

Status of herpetofauna at Bangladesh Livestock Research Institute (BLRI), Savar, Dhaka

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Abstract

A study was conducted on the "Herpetofaunal Diversity in Bangladesh Livestock Research Institute (BLRI)" between August 2007 and July 2008 by using strip transect method. A total of 21 species of 10 Herpetofaunal families were found in BLRI during this period. 8 species (38.10%) were of 4 amphibian families; among which Ranidae contained most species (19.05%) and *Fejervarya limnocharis* were most frequent (100%) whereas *Polypedates leucomystax* were at risk. On the other hand, 13 species (61.90%) were of 6 reptilian families; among which Colubridae contained most species (23.81%) and *Calotes versicolor* were most frequent species (93.33%) whereas *Varanus flavescens*, *Ramphotyphlops braminus*, *Amphiesma stolata* and *Oligodon taeniolata* were at risk. A total of 11 threatened species were found in this area.

Key words: Diversity, herpetofauna, BLRI.

INTRODUCTION

Bangladesh is a global biodiversity hotspot in tropical Asia which contains a unique and highly threatened biota (Encyclopedia of Flora and Fauna of Bangladesh, 2009). Unfortunately, no in-depth study or survey has yet been done on the status and distribution of amphibians of Bangladesh (Chowdhury, 1996). Herpetofauna of Bangladesh are neglected and poorly known (IUCN, 2000). In contrast to India and Sri Lanka, fewer attempts have been made to document the species diversity and little effort has been devoted to resolve species evolutionary affinities (Molur, 2008). The first herpetofaunal checklist was produced by IUCN Bangladesh in 2000, which merely an extracted list based on the collections is made by the British over century ago and some borrowed works from neighboring countries (Reza, 2009). According to IUCN (2000) there are 131 species of reptiles and amphibians have been reported from the country so far, and 112 of them (85%) are facing conservation threats. About 43% of amphibian and reptile species were categorized as Data Deficient, indicating lack of even basic information. Bangladesh Livestock Research Institute (BLRI) though a very small part of the country, it contains a number of habitat types which are very much suitable for the herpetofauna and represent more or less most part of the country. For these reasons this area was selected to conduct a survey on herpetofaunal diversity.

Study area: Bangladesh Livestock Research Institute (BLRI) is situated between 90°14.35' N to 90°17.55' N and 23°52.30' E to 23°55.00' E (Fig. 1). It is about 33 km north-west of Dhaka City, under Savar Thana of Dhaka District. It is bounded by Youth

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Development Center and Central cattle breeding & Dairy Farm on the south, Jahangirnagar University on the west, dividing by Dhaka-Aricha Road, Savar Cantonment on the north, dividing by Bishmile-Jirabo Road, and free space and some garments on the east. The total area of BLRI is 600 acres. It is of diverse habitats for herpetofauna. There are forest patches, woodlands, bushy jungles, grass lands, cultivated lands and many temporary and permanent water bodies are present. The climatic condition of BLRI was moderate (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Climatic condition of the study area during conducting the research. Here the data shown in-Temperature- °C, Relative Humidity-% and Rainfall-Inch

Fig. 1. Satellite map (image) of Bangladesh Livestock Research Institute

METHODS AND MATERIALS

To collect the Herpetofaunal individuals and observe them Strip Transect Method was followed. This method used as it is most feasible in determining the Herpetofaunal diversity than other methods. For instance, Feeroz (2001, 2003), Feeroz *et al.* (1995) and Ahmed (2007) had followed this method to determine the wildlife diversity. 15 transect lines were taken with 10m width, 5m on each side. Roads and foot-paths were taken as base lines. Maximum trips were conducted in rainy season, while no trip in winter season.

Methods described by Verma & Agarwal (1998) were followed for the determination of frequency, density and abundance. In order to determine the status of Herpetofauna of BLRI methods of categorization from IUCN, 2000, were modified as follows–

Table 1. Status categories with number range

Category	Symbol	Number of individuals
At Risk	AR	1-5
Rare	R	6-20
Lower Risk	LR	21-40
Common	C	41-150
Very Common	VC	151-above

*Modified from IUCN, 2000

The observed individuals were identified through matching the characteristics described and photographs given in books like 'The book of Indian reptiles and Amphibians (Daniel, 2002), Decline amphibian population: A global Phenomena (Blaustein & Wake, 1995), The Fauna of British India, Including Ceylon and Burma (Boulenger, 1890), Red book of threatened amphibia and reptiles of Bangladesh (IUCN, 2000). The Fauna of British India including Ceylon and Burma (Smith, 1934), Herpetology- An Introductory Biology of Amphibians and Reptiles (Zug, 1973), Protected Areas of Bangladesh – A Guide to Wildlife (Khan, 2008) etc. At the same time, help from the experts was also taken in order to identify the individuals.

Sweep net, Snake stick, Plastic bottles and Polythene bags; Slide calipers, Tape, Scale and Field books; Chloroform, Formalin, Alcohol etc. were used during study period to collect, identify and preserve the specimens.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 21 species of herpetofauna were found during the study period (Table 2), from August'07-July'08, in BLRI. 8 species of these were of Amphibian and the rest 13 species were of Reptilian (Fig. 3). All these species were of 4 amphibian families of the order Anura and 6 reptilian families of the order Lacertilia and Serpentes. Among herpetofaunal families the Colubridae, a reptilian family contained most species (23.81%). Bufonidae and Rhacophoridae of Amphibia and Agamidae, Scincidae and Typhlopidae of Reptilia combinedly contained least species (4.76%) (Fig. 4).

Among amphibians there were only 2 species Very Common (VC) and 1 At Risk (AR) (Table 2) whereas only 1 species was VC and 4 were AR among reptilians (Table 2). A total of 987 herpetofaunal individuals were found in BLRI during this period. Out of these, 577 individuals were of amphibian species and 410 individuals were of reptilian species (Fig. 5 & 6). However, *Fejervarya limnocharis* were most frequent (100%), most dense (15.27) and most abundant (15.27) and *Polypedates leucomystax* were least frequent (20%), least dense (0.27) and least abundant (1.33) among amphibians (Fig. 5). On the other hand, *Calotes versicolor* were most frequent (93.33%) but *Hemidactylus frenatus* were most dense (14.47) and most abundant (21.7) and *V. flavescens* was least frequent (6.67%) and *Ramphotyphlops braminus* were least abundant (1) and both were least dense (0.13) among reptilians (Fig. 6). The found amphibian families represent all the four families that are locally found in whole Bangladesh, as recorded by IUCN (2000). Moreover there were 8 amphibian species out of 22 species (IUCN, 2000) of Bangladesh recorded in BLRI. Furthermore, this area includes *Fejervarya limnocharis* which wasn't recorded by IUCN. On the other hand the reptilian orders of BLRI represent 50% of total orders found in whole Bangladesh as recorded by IUCN (2000). BLRI contained many country wide and globally threatened herpetofaunal species. These species consist of 2 EN and 1 VU amphibian species and 3 VU, 1 EN and 1 DD reptilian species.

Table 2. List of amphibian and reptilian species of BLRI with their status

Class	Order	Family	Common Name	Species	Status (BLRI)	Status (Country)
Amphibia	Anura	Bufonidae	Common Toad	<i>Duttaphrynus melanostictus</i>	C	NO
		Microhylidae	Ornate Narrow-Mouthed Frog	<i>Microhyla ornata</i>	C	VU
			Grey Balloon Frog	<i>Uperodon globulosus</i>	R	EN
			Skipper Frog	<i>Euphlyctis cyanophlyctis</i>	VC	NO
		Ranidae	Fejervarya	<i>Fejervarya limnocharis</i>	VC	NR
			Taipeh Frog	<i>Hylarana taipehensis</i>	R	EN
			Bull Frog	<i>Hoplobatrachus tigerinus</i>	R	NO
		Rhacophoridae	Tree Frog	<i>Polypedates leucomystax</i>	AR	NO
		Reptilia	Lacertilia	Geckonidae	Gecko	<i>Gekko gekko</i>
Agamidae	Common House Lizard			<i>Hemidactylus frenatus</i>	VC	NO
	House Lizard			<i>H. brooki</i>	LR	NO
	Common Garden Lizard			<i>Calotes versicolor</i>	C	NO
Scincidae	Common Skink			<i>Mabuya carinata</i>	LR	NO
Varanidae	Bengal Monitor		<i>Varanus bengalensis</i>	R	VU	
	Yellow Monitor		<i>V. flavescens</i>	AR	EN	
	Typhlopidae		Common Worm Snake	<i>Ramphotyphlops braminus</i>	AR	NO
Serpentes	Colubridae		Checkered Keelback	<i>Xenochrophis piscator</i>	LR	NO
			Common Smooth Water Snake	<i>Enhydris enhydris</i>	R	NO
			Stripped Keelback	<i>Amphiesma stolata</i>	AR	NO
			Rat Snake	<i>Ptyas mucosus</i>	R	VU
			Russell's Kukri Snake	<i>Oligodon taeniolata</i>	AR	DD

NB: At Risk (AR), Rare (R), Lower Risk (LR), Common (C), Very Common (VC), Not Threatened (NO), Endangered (EN), Vulnerable (VU), Not Recorded (NR).

Fig. 5. Frequency, density and abundance of amphibian species of BLRI

Fig. 6. Frequency, density and abundance of amphibian species of BLRI

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